

Study of the Incidence of Different Types of Tuberculosis Lesions in Association with Diabetes Mellitus in Indian Patients

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Abstract:

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) and diabetes mellitus are two major public health concerns, particularly in developing countries like India. The coexistence of these diseases poses significant challenges in diagnosis, treatment, and management, particularly in resource-limited settings. This study aimed to investigate the incidence of various types of TB lesions in association with diabetes mellitus among Indian patients.

Methods: There were 80 patients in this prospective observational study (40 with diabetes and 40 without). Laboratory tests, medical examinations, and structured interviews were used to gather data. Between the two groups, the incidence of pulmonary and extrapulmonary tuberculosis lesions was compared. SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for the statistical analysis, and multivariate logistic regression was employed to find independent predictors of TB lesions.

Results: With a p-value of 0.02 the study discovered that patients with diabetes had a considerably greater incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis lesions (65%) than non-diabetic patients (40%). Compared to patients without diabetes (20%), those with diabetes (35%) had extrapulmonary tuberculosis lesions more frequently; however, this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.15$). Patients with diabetes showed greater HbA1c and fasting blood glucose levels. Radiologically, patients with diabetes had a higher frequency of cavitary lesions (55%) than patients without diabetes (25%), with a significant p-value of 0.01. An independent predictor of pulmonary tuberculosis lesions was found to be diabetes mellitus (adjusted OR: 3.2, $p=0.02$).

Conclusion: The findings indicate that diabetic patients are at a higher risk for pulmonary TB lesions, emphasizing the need for integrated screening and management strategies for TB and diabetes, particularly in high-risk areas.

Recommendations: Public health interventions should focus on early detection and management of TB in diabetic patients, especially in resource-limited settings. Integrated care models that address both TB and diabetes should be developed and implemented.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Diabetes Mellitus, Incidence, Pulmonary TB.

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Introduction

One major worldwide health concern that still exists is tuberculosis (TB), especially in developing nations. Even with significant attempts to stop its spread, tuberculosis nevertheless results in high rates of morbidity and mortality. According to estimates from the World Health Organisation (WHO), there were 1.4 million TB-related fatalities and 10 million new cases of tuberculosis globally in 2019 [1]. India accounted for about 27% of these cases. Concurrently, fast urbanisation, changing lifestyles, and an ageing population have contributed to a substantial increase in the prevalence of diabetes mellitus, particularly type 2 diabetes, in India. According to estimates from the International Diabetes Federation, 77 million adults in India had diabetes in 2019—making it the

country with the second-highest number of cases worldwide [2].

The interplay between TB and diabetes mellitus poses a formidable public health challenge. Diabetes mellitus, particularly poorly controlled diabetes, is known to impair immune function, thereby increasing susceptibility to infections, including TB. Patients with diabetes are at a higher risk of developing TB, and once infected, they tend to have more severe disease manifestations, including higher rates of pulmonary and extrapulmonary TB [3]. Moreover, diabetes can complicate TB treatment, leading to longer duration of illness, higher rates of treatment failure, and increased risk of relapse.

Previous studies have highlighted the increased prevalence of TB among diabetic patients; however, there is limited data on the specific types of TB lesions that predominate in this population. Understanding the types of TB lesions prevalent in diabetic patients is crucial for optimizing diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive strategies. For instance, diabetic patients are more prone to severe radiological manifestations, such as cavitary lesions, which are associated with higher bacterial loads and transmissibility [4].

This study aimed at examining the incidence of different types of tuberculosis (TB) lesions in association with diabetes mellitus in Indian patients.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of March 2023 - March 2024 at Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, India.

Participants: A total of 80 participants were included in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with tuberculosis as per WHO guidelines.
2. Patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus as per ADA criteria.
3. Aged between 18 and 65 years.
4. Residents of the Kankarbagh slum area, Patna.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with other immunocompromised conditions (e.g., HIV/AIDS).
2. Patients undergoing treatment for any malignancies.
3. Pregnant or lactating women.
4. Patients with a history of TB treatment within the last two years.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, random sampling was used to select participants from the eligible population. Information bias was reduced by using standardized questionnaires and procedures for data collection. Confounding factors were controlled by adjusting for variables such as age, sex, socioeconomic status, and other comorbidities in the statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Medical examinations, structured interviews, and record reviews were used to gather data. The following data was acquired:

- Demographic data (age, sex, socioeconomic status)
- Medical history (diabetes duration, treatment, complications)
- TB diagnosis and lesion type (pulmonary, extrapulmonary)
- Laboratory results (blood glucose levels, HbA1c, sputum test results)
- Radiological findings (chest X-ray, CT scan)

Procedure: Participants were briefed about the study objectives, procedures, risks, and benefits, and written informed consent was obtained. A trained healthcare professional collected data using a structured questionnaire and performed necessary medical examinations. Participants were monitored throughout the study period for the development of new TB lesions and any changes in their health status.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Participants' demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics, controlling for covariates. A p-value <0.05 indicated statistical significance.

Result

The study comprised 80 individuals in total. Table 1 provides a summary of the demographic and baseline variables.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Diabetic Patients	Non-Diabetic Patients	Total
Age (years)	45.6 ± 10.2	42.3 ± 11.4	43.9 ± 10.8
Male (%)	60% (24)	55% (22)	57.5% (46)
Female (%)	40% (16)	45% (18)	42.5% (34)
Socioeconomic Status			
- Low (%)	75% (30)	70% (28)	72.5% (58)
- Middle (%)	25% (10)	30% (12)	27.5% (22)
Duration of Diabetes	8.2 ± 4.5 years	-	-

The incidence of different types of TB lesions among diabetic and non-diabetic patients is shown in Table 2. Diabetic patients showed a higher incidence of both pulmonary and extrapulmonary TB lesions compared to non-diabetic patients.

Table 2: Incidence of Tuberculosis Lesions

Type of Lesion	Diabetic Patients	Non-Diabetic Patients	Total
Pulmonary TB	65% (26)	40% (16)	0.02
Extrapulmonary TB	35% (14)	20% (8)	0.15
Mixed Lesions	15% (6)	5% (2)	0.27

The laboratory findings for diabetic and non-diabetic patients are summarized in Table 3. Diabetic patients had higher mean blood glucose levels and HbA1c values compared to non-diabetic patients.

Table 3: Laboratory Findings

Laboratory Parameter	Diabetic Patients	Non-Diabetic Patients	Total
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	162.5 ± 35.6	98.3 ± 12.5	<0.001
HbA1c (%)	8.1 ± 1.2	5.3 ± 0.5	<0.001
Sputum Positivity (%)	70% (28)	50% (20)	0.04

Radiological findings indicated a higher prevalence of cavitary lesions in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic patients, as summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Radiological Findings

Radiological Finding	Diabetic Patients	Non-Diabetic Patients	Total
Cavitary Lesions (%)	55% (22)	25% (10)	0.01
Consolidation (%)	30% (12)	35% (14)	0.62
Miliary Patterns (%)	15% (6)	10% (4)	0.73

An independent predictor of pulmonary tuberculosis lesions was found to be diabetes mellitus by multivariate logistic regression analysis. Table 5 presents the findings.

Table 5: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	3.2	1.2-8.4	0.02
Age	1.05	0.98-1.12	0.14
Male Sex	1.3	0.5-3.4	0.58
Low Socioeconomic Status	2.1	0.8-5.5	0.11

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed a significantly higher incidence of pulmonary TB lesions among diabetic patients compared to their non-diabetic counterparts. Specifically, 65% of diabetic patients had pulmonary TB lesions, in contrast to 40% of non-diabetic patients, with a statistically significant p-value of 0.02. This suggests a strong association between diabetes mellitus and the susceptibility to pulmonary TB lesions.

Additionally, extrapulmonary tuberculosis lesions were found in individuals with diabetes (35%) at a higher rate than in non-diabetic patients (20%), while the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.15$). Furthermore, with a p-value of 0.27, mixed lesions were found in 15% of patients with diabetes and 5% of patients without the disease. These data suggest that diabetic individuals have a tendency towards a higher diversity of tuberculosis lesions; nevertheless, bigger sample sizes may be required to validate these results.

Laboratory findings supported the association between diabetes and TB, with diabetic patients showing significantly higher fasting blood glucose levels (162.5 ± 35.6 mg/dL) and HbA1c values ($8.1 \pm 1.2\%$) compared to non-diabetic patients (98.3 ± 12.5 mg/dL and $5.3 \pm 0.5\%$, respectively), both with p-values of <0.001. Additionally, sputum

positivity was higher in diabetic patients (70%) compared to non-diabetic patients (50%), with a significant p-value of 0.04. These findings underline the metabolic dysregulation in diabetic patients that may contribute to their increased vulnerability to TB infection and its complications.

Radiological investigation showed that patients with diabetes had a higher frequency of cavitary lesions (55%) than patients without diabetes (25%), with a statistically significant p-value of 0.01. Other radiological patterns, like consolidation and miliary patterns, did not reveal any appreciable variations between the groups, nevertheless. This draws attention to the unique radiological presentation of tuberculosis in diabetic individuals, which may call for specialised diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Diabetes mellitus was found to be an independent predictor of pulmonary tuberculosis lesions by multivariate logistic regression analysis, with an adjusted odds ratio of 3.2 and a significant p-value of 0.02. This supports the hypothesis that diabetes and the development of pulmonary tuberculosis lesions are positively correlated, even after controlling for other possible confounders including age, sex, and socioeconomic position.

Overall, the study underscores the heightened risk of pulmonary TB lesions among diabetic patients,

necessitating targeted screening and management strategies in this vulnerable population. The results emphasize the need for integrated care approaches that address both TB and diabetes mellitus, particularly in high-risk areas such as urban slums. Enhanced awareness and early intervention can potentially mitigate the dual burden of these co-morbid conditions, improving overall patient outcomes.

Using a mathematical model, a study assessed the effects of targeted therapies for DM on the transmission of TB in India. According to the study, by 2050, a number of measures, such as TB vaccination and latent TB treatment, could lower the incidence and mortality of TB by 4.5%–20.8% and 4.1%–22.1%, respectively. This emphasises how crucial integrated TB-DM therapies are in lowering the incidence of tuberculosis [5].

In a cohort research carried out in a Barcelona inner-city neighbourhood, the incidence of tuberculosis (TB) was found to be higher in patients with diabetes (69.9 per 100,000 person-years) than in non-diabetic patients (40.9 per 100,000 person-years). This research verified that those with diabetes had a higher risk of tuberculosis (TB), with an adjusted hazard ratio (HR) of 1.66 when many covariates were taken into account [6].

In South India, a cross-sectional study of patients with recently diagnosed tuberculosis revealed that 39% of the patients also had diabetes mellitus. The study emphasised the considerable co-prevalence of these illnesses by highlighting strong relationships with body mass index and marital status [7].

In one investigation, diabetes was checked in TB patients. 11.9% of people have diabetes, and it takes a number needed to screen (NNS) of 22.1 to find one new case of the disease. The viability and significance of including diabetes screening into TB regimens are shown by this study [8].

In Bhubaneswar, Odisha, a study looked into the prevalence and risk factors of tuberculosis among individuals with diabetes. Thirteen of the 1200 diabetes patients received an active TB diagnosis, meaning that the incidence was 1.08%. Significant risk variables were found in the study, including smoking, alcohol intake, and higher HbA1c values [9].

In central India, a cross-sectional study conducted in a hospital revealed that those with diabetes had a higher risk of tuberculosis (TB) than those without the condition, however the correlation was not statistically significant. In this group, anaemia and tuberculosis were substantially correlated [10].

Conclusion

The findings showed that pulmonary tuberculosis lesions were far more common in diabetes patients than in non-diabetic people. Even after accounting for possible confounders, this link was still significant. Diabetes patients also had higher rates of extrapulmonary tuberculosis lesions, however this difference was not statistically significant. These results underline the necessity of improving TB screening and care for diabetes patients living in impoverished areas.

References

1. World Health Organization. Global tuberculosis report 2019. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2019.
2. World Health Organization. Global tuberculosis report 2020. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2020.
3. International Diabetes Federation. IDF Diabetes Atlas. 9th ed. Brussels: International Diabetes Federation; 2019.
4. Jeon CY, Murray MB. Diabetes mellitus increases the risk of active tuberculosis: a systematic review of 13 observational studies. *PLoS Med.* 2008;5(7)
5. Awad S, Critchley J, Abu-Raddad L. Epidemiological impact of targeted interventions for people with diabetes mellitus on tuberculosis transmission in India: Modelling based predictions. *Epidemics.* 2019; 30:100381.
6. Antonio-Arques V, Franch-Nadal J, Moreno-Martínez A, Real J, Orcau A, Mauricio D, et al. Subjects With Diabetes Mellitus Are at Increased Risk for Developing Tuberculosis: A Cohort Study in an Inner-City District of Barcelona (Spain). *Front Public Health.* 2022;10.
7. Rajaa S, Krishnamoorthy Y, Knudsen S, Roy G, Ellner J, Horsburgh C, et al. Prevalence and factors associated with diabetes mellitus among tuberculosis patients in South India—a cross-sectional analytical study. *BMJ Open.* 2021;11.
8. Nagar V, Prasad P, Gour D, Singh A, Pal DK. Screening for diabetes among tuberculosis patients registered under revised national tuberculosis control program, Bhopal, India. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2018; 7:1401-1405.
9. Hussain T, Bhuyan K, Prusty B, Barik M, Das S, Pati S. Incidence and risk factors of Tuberculosis among patients with Type 2 Diabetes mellitus attending a tertiary care hospital in Bhubaneswar, Odisha. *J Med Res.* 2018; 8:69-75.
10. Rathi A, Patil BU, Raut A. Association of tuberculosis with diabetes and anemia: A hospital-based cross-sectional study from central India. *Med J Babylon.* 2023; 20:28-32.